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Impact of Information Communication and Technology on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria

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***Abstract:** This paper assessed the impact of information communication technologies on teachers' job performance in public Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. The paper is a review paper. The paper used secondary data to support every point raised. The paper employed systematic review system to collect data online and in the print resources. The paper concluded that ICT enhanced the teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria. The paper noted specifically that ICT aided teachers in lesson presentation, lesson plan and lesson note writing and students data computation. Based on this findings, the paper recommends that the government should provide all ICT infrastructure facilities needed to effectively carry out teaching and learning in all the public secondary schools. Government should organize capacity building on ICT usage constantly for teachers in all the public secondary schools.*

***Key words:** Information Communication, Technology, Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD).*

Introduction

The Nigerian secondary school also known as Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) is the education children receive after a successful completion of nine years of Basic Education and passing the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate Examination (JAISCE). It includes: (i) senior secondary education, (ii) higher school; and (iii) continuing education given in Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs) to either Basic Education graduates who are not proceeding to Senior Secondary Schools, or Senior Secondary graduates that are not proceeding to the tertiary level, as a means of preparing them for the world of work, wealth creation and entrepreneurship (National policy on education 2014).

The objectives of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) according to (National policy on education 2014) are to: a. provide holders of the Basic Education Certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate with opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethnic background; b. offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, disposition, opportunities and future roles; c. provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades; d. provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job-specific skills for self-reliance, and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development; e. develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world's cultural heritage; f. inspire students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; g. foster patriotism, national unity and security education with emphasis on the common ties in spite of our diversity; and h. raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think in dependently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour. (National policy on education 2014). The realization of the objectives of Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) depends on the availability of materials and human resources available in the educational institutions. The human resources is made up of the teachers and non-teaching staff while the materials resources include ICT resources etc. (Ogunode, Somadina, Yahaya, & Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2021). The teachers uses ICT to support the implementation of school curriculum. The school teacher is one of the school stakeholders. The teacher is regarded as one of the crucial member of the school community whose roles cannot be underscored. Noun (2012) submitted that a teacher is described as the professional, who imparts knowledge, learning experiences at his disposal to stimulate, guide, direct and facilitate learners to acquire adequate mastery of the skills being imparted. Teachers' job performance according Zaifada, et al, (2023) include writing of lesson note, lesson plan, organization of instrument materials, assigning of test and examination, marking, representing of school, extra-curriculum activities and motivation of students. The teachers' job performances are all activities and programmes the teachers carry out in the school and the extent to which the activities are achieved. ICT may assist the teachers to carry out teaching programme in the schools. It is important to examine the impact of ICT on teachers' job performance in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2013) stated that ICT can contribute to universal access to education, equity in education, the delivery of quality learning and teaching, teachers' professional development, efficient management, governance, and administration. nd development of the nation socially and economically. United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2005) viewed ICT as a combination of all the computers, telecommunication, and media technologies. They are also electronic technologies used for accessing, processing, gathering, manipulating, and presenting or communicating information in the education system. Vijayan (2011) defined ICT as the application of computers and technologies for acquisition, organization, storage, retrieval, and dissemination of information. Malanga (2015) explained the definition further to mean a revolution that provides the platform and technical means of handling information and communication.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is an umbrella term that includes any communication device or application encompassing radio, television, mobile phones, computer hardware and software, internet, satellite systems and so on as well as the various services and applications associated with them such as video conferencing and distance learning. It is the use of

scientific devices in providing information faster and better (Patrick. & Brenda. 2018). ICT is defined by Ayannuga (2009) as the marriage that exist between computer system and communication which can be described as the use of computer-based technology and internet to make information and communication services available to a greater number of users. Information and communication technology as a set of tools that help a person work with information and perform tasks related to the information process (Uwabueze & Ozioko 2011).

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is the integrated use of electronic tools and systems, including computers, telecommunications, and media technologies, that facilitate the collection, storage, processing, transmission, and sharing of information. In educational settings, ICT encompasses a wide range of hardware, software, and networks that support various activities such as teaching, learning, administration, and research. These technologies enable users to access and manipulate data, enhance communication, and streamline processes, ultimately transforming the way information is delivered and received within institutions. ICT plays a vital role in modern education by improving access to knowledge, fostering collaboration, and promoting innovative learning experiences (Ogunode, Olatunde-Aiyedun, Ukozor, & Ayeni, 2024). ICT has improved the value of education by providing access to a great variety of educational resources and by enabling participatory pedagogies. It also improves the management of education through more efficient administrative processes, including human resource management, monitoring and evaluation, and resource sharing (Unwin, 2004).ICT aids teachers job performance in the schools.

Teacher job performance is the extent to which the teachers are carrying out their official responsibilities in the schools (Ogunode, Olowonefa, & Ayoko 2023). Casting (2016) defined job performance as execution, conduct, compliance or conformity with stated decisions or directives issued by a super-ordinate or demanded by a job. This shows that performance of any job must be according to the pattern set performing such tasks. Teachers' job Performance in secondary schools is highly influenced by many factors such as motivation, qualifications, school climate, among others (Atiya & Palwasha, ND). Teacher job performance refer to the execution of instructor's responsibilities and tasks in the educational institutions Josiah, Audu and Ogunode, (2023).. Teacher job performance is the level by which the teachers accomplished their given functions and assignment in the schools (Ogunode 2023). Teachers' job performance is the extent they are committed to effective pedagogical delivery and exhibit uprightness and academic excellence in conducting academic activities (Uko *et al.*, 2015). Teachers' job performance is the ability of teachers to display the right attitude to work by being committed and dedicated to the teaching job and making frantic efforts towards the accomplishment of school goals and objectives (Akporehe, et al2023).

Teachers' job performance has been described as their level of involvement in the day to day running of school. It is referred to as the measure of teacher's level of effectiveness in relation to their expected responsibilities in their school. It is used to assess whether a teacher carries out his or her job well or not in terms of teaching, discipline, lesson plan, lesson delivery and commitment (Awodiji, 2018). Bassey, Agbade & Ogunode (2023) and Ogunode and Josiah (2023) defined teacher job performance as the extent to which the teachers have attained the objectives of teaching in the schools. Teachers' job performance is the level at which the instructor has been able to execute the assigned functions in the school environment. The job performance of teachers is very important to the school because the success or failure of the teachers affects the school system. From the above, teacher job performance is the level of execution of official assignments within a timeframe in school (Ogunode & Ajayi 2022).

Data Analysis on Impact of Information Communication Technologies on Teachers' job Performance

Application of ICT in the schools have led to effective school administration and management. ICT have increase the effectiveness of school operation. ICT is used by both the school administrators, students and teachers. ICT have proven to be very effective in the implementation of teaching and learning in the schools. ICT have assisted teachers to perform their official responsibilities such as lesson presentation and lesson note writing (Akarakiri, 2018). Eric, and Siminialayi, (2021) and Ogunode, Lawal, and Olubunmi (2021) concluded that deployment of ICT tools such as internet, e-mail, computer, video camera, projector, in class and conferences have made it possible to overcomes barriers of space and time, and opens new possibilities for teaching and aiding teachers to implement the school curriculum.

The application of computers in the teaching and learning is really topical; and thus, computer programme facilitates communication between students and teacher and beyond the classroom setting, like distanced students' instruction and aids teachers' productivities in the classroom (Ali, Haolader, & Muhammad, 2013). Mouza (2002), the application of computer in teaching learning process offers various importance such as cheap accessible and instantaneous information, enormous potential for interactive and media-rich communication, and powerful educational tools that will improve students' academic works and teachers job performance (Allison, & Allison, 2014). MartinandOfori-Attah (2005) identified that teachers could use computer for different purposes like teaching purpose, administration purposes, and to support his or her functions such as management of students data (Deebom, & Zite, 2016; Ziden., Ismail, Spian, & Kumutha, 2011).

ICT have been described by Abara, et al (2021), as one of the educational resources available for teachers to execute their functions in the schools. They went further and observed that information communication technology have provided opportunities for the school administrators, teachers and students to achieve the school objectives hereby assisting teachers to implement the curriculum in the schools. Muhammed (2017) submitted that ICT is one of the instructional aid available for the teachers in this 21st century for the implementation of the school curriculum. ICT can help teachers in lesson note writing, lesson presentation in class, marking of notes, giving of assignments, assessing students' achievement, compilation of report sheet and setting of examination questions fast and simple. James (2017) posited that the use of ICT in various lessons by teachers in school allows: to develop the ability of students to navigate the information flows of the surrounding world; to organize at the same time children with different abilities and skills; to master practical ways of working with information; to develop skills to exchange information using modern technical means; and to intensify the cognitive activity of students.

The teacher's roles in using computer for instruction are further conceptualized as spending his time in leading group discussions and in working with students individually and in small groups using laboratory work where applicable (Hambagba, 2015; Idris 2016; Goh, & Sigala, 2020). The teacher is not a spectator of incomprehension but guides the students in the multitude of diversified documents to make relevant choices. He is a guarantor of assimilation as well as facilitator to help learners' use and access knowledge in computer education. McCormick (1993), computers can be used to diversify, develop and improve the pedagogical relation of teaching and learning. It provides appropriate record-keeping and thereby monitors students' progress (Idris, 2016).

Patrick and Brenda (2018) write that ICT is not just the bloom of the education system, but also the primary and secondary options required to improve effective and meaningful interaction between

teachers and students of secondary schools and to improve teachers' job performance in the schools. It has the power to make teachers students enjoy things that they would normally find time-consuming and difficult because it involves practical teaching and student-centered and not teachers talking and writing on the chalkboard and student copying from the chalkboard into their notebook without engaging in practical teaching which makes learning boring. ICT is a teaching tool that improves the quality of secondary school student's education and support teachers' work. ICT usage in teaching in public secondary schools will aid effective teachings and learning and help the students acquire necessary skills that will enable them to contribute to the growth, improvement, and development of the nation socially and economically (Etejere, & Ogundele, 2013;Etudor-Eyo, Ante, & Emah, 2012).

ICT will also help issues like effective classroom management, collaborative learning, self-study, course/subject organization, and enhance effective communication between peers, teachers, and student-teacher. In today's modern-day teaching, students partake actively and vigorously in the process unlike before where a teacher will stand in front of a class and giving lectures to students without them contributing to the subject or topic (Ogunode, Ohibime, Okwelogu, & Musa, 2021;Abubakar 2016 cited Ajayi, 2008).

Information and communication technology has had more impact on administrative services such as admission, registration, fee payment and purchasing than on the fundamentals of classroom teaching and learning and teachers' job performance. Information and communication technology has not revolutionalized the classroom only, it is changing the teaching and learning experience of teachers and students by providing them with opportunities to carry out research and carry out distance teaching and learning (Gambari and Okoli 2007).

In conclusion, Ogundele and Etejere (2013) discovered that computer literacy encourages teachers' appreciation and utilization of computers during teaching learning processes and ICT aids teachers' job effectiveness in areas as; record keeping, school discipline, and supports students' academic performance. Ogunode, Jegede, & Musa, (2020) and Ogundele et al also revealed that computer literate teachers perform better in the schools than non-computer literate teachers in the schools by making use of computers during their teaching, the use of computers arouse students' interest in the teachings which supports effective student academic performance and teachers' job performance.

Findings

The paper revealed that ICT enhanced the teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria. The paper noted specifically that ICT aided teachers in lesson presentation, lesson plan and lesson note writing and students data computation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper discussed the impact of information communication technologies on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria. The paper concluded that ICT enhanced the teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria. The paper noted specifically that ICT aided teachers in lesson presentation, lesson plan and lesson note writing and students data computation.

Based on this findings, the paper recommends that the government should provide all ICT infrastructure facilities needed to effectively carry out teaching and learning in all the public secondary schools. Government should organize capacity building on ICT usage constantly for teachers in all the public secondary schools.

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